

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JAIN****FIRST NAME: SANJAY****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied **UK** conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author **did** use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author **did** use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: **MSWord for Mac 16.85 (24051214)**

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is not Plagiarism?

- When the writer uses a source of information and gives credit to another writer.
- When the writer uses a source of information and does not give credit to another writer.
- When the writer uses a source of information and gives credit to the author of the source of information.¹**
- When the writer uses a source of information and gives credit to the publisher of the source of information.

2. Which style guide does EUCLID recommend?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- The Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association (APA).
 - The Modern Language Association's (MLA) Handbook.
 - Oxford Standard for Citation of Legal Authorities (OSCALA).
 - Chicago Rules (Turabian).²**
3. What is the meaning of the term *problem* for researchers?
- A question to which no one has yet found an answer.
 - It is something which we try to avoid.
 - A question that researchers seek out or invent.³**
 - A question of significance that readers recognize needs a solution.
4. What is the meaning of *applied* research for academic researchers?
- Academic researcher addressing practical problem.⁴**
 - Academic researcher addressing conceptual problem.
 - Academic researcher conversing with the reader.
 - A question of significance that the researcher recognizes needs a solution.
5. Which of the following does not refer to the *author-date style*?
- Turabian style.
 - Chicago author-date.

² Ibid., 41.

³ Kate Turabian *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 28.

⁴ Ibid., 22.

- Reference list style.
- Oxford Standard for Citation of Legal Authorities (OSCALA).**⁵
6. Which of the following changes is not permissible when incorporating a quotation into your text?
- Correcting a typographical error in the original text.
- Quoting from older text by altering the idiosyncrasies of spelling.
- Altering the initial letter from capital to lower case or vice versa and noting the change.**⁶
- Deleting or changing a colon or semicolon to a period or a comma.
7. Which of the following is not included in a dissertation concept paper?
- Abstract.**⁷
- Statement of the Problem.
- Research Questions.
- Research Design.
8. Which of the following is the source of potential bias in dissertation research?
- Education bias.
- Construct bias.

⁵ Ibid., 228.

⁶ Ibid., 275.

⁷ James P Sampson *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

- Age bias.
- Population bias.**⁸

9. Which of the following is an *English* word?

- offense.
- tariff.**⁹
- exemple.
- correspondance.

10. Which of the following is not a guideline for inclusive language?

- Use expressions such as ‘old people/persons’ or ‘the elderly’.**¹⁰
- Avoid word choices which may be interpreted as implying that one gender is the norm.
- Avoid using words containing ‘man’.
- When referring to relationships, use the terms ‘spouse’ or ‘partner’.

⁸ Ibid., 8.

⁹ European Commission *English Style Guide A Handbook for Authors and Translators in European Commission* 8th ed. (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021), 20.

¹⁰ Ibid., 63.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, And Dissertations*. 9th Edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.